
Constraints on rice yield

A perspective study on self-sufficiency in rice production in five selected countries of West Africa

E. Lord, economist, United Nations Economic Commission for Africa, Food and Agriculture Organization Joint Agriculture Division, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia

A mid 1975 study in Gambia, Ghana, Liberia, Nigeria, and Sierra Leone sought to provide perspective on the rice situation to help the countries to increase rice production and to attain self-sufficiency. Increasing demand for commercial rice in the West African countries is due to rapid urbanization and increasing money incomes. Imports have been increasing rapidly. Much domestic rice is consumed on the farms where it is grown as noncommercial food crop. For production to increase, rice must be made a commercial crop and a marketing system must be developed.

The main conclusions are listed below.

1. Rice production will remain static as long as governments do not intervene.

2. If governments intervene and effectively attack the key constraints, production can be increased relatively quickly.

3. More emphasis should be placed on economic and social constraints and less on agronomic constraints.

4. Programs and schemes for increased rice production must offer attractive financial incentives and be socially acceptable to have significant impact.

5. Such constraints as animal pests, lack of marketing facilities, high capital cost, low profitability, and hard work can offset much of the potential gain that might result from new technological practices and inputs.

Another project will analyze in more detail the economics of present and new technology, marketing constraints, and labor use problems, particularly the role of women in rice production. *W*

A review of the research and methodology of the International Rice Agroeconomic Network

R. W. Herdt, Agricultural Economics Department, International Rice Research Institute

Six papers, summarizing results of experiments on farmers' fields and of coordinated farm surveys by the International Rice Agroeconomic Network (IRAEN), were presented at a November 1976 meeting in Yogyakarta, Indonesia. Twenty-six rice agronomists and economists from Bangladesh, Indonesia, Sri Lanka, Taiwan, Thailand, and the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI) discussed the studies designed to determine major biophysical constraints on rice yields, and the socioeconomic reasons for the persistence of those constraints. Methodology used by IRAEN research groups was reviewed and modified. A plan was outlined to achieve increased uniformity in methodology in the 1977 work. It is anticipated that the papers will be published by IRRI in 1977. *W*

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two paragraphs and a table, figure, or photograph. They are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

Individuals, organizations, and media are invited to quote or reprint articles or excerpts from articles in the IRRN. Duplicate prints of photos and illustrations are available to media on request from the Office of Information Services, IRRI. Persons who wish additional details of information presented in IRRN should write directly to the authors.

The International Rice Research Institute
P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines

Stamp